

Teachers' Perceptions of Storytelling Strategy for Improving Pupils' Academic Achievement in Reading Comprehension in English Studies

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Abstract

This study was carried out to determine teachers' perception of story-telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in Awka South LGEA. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population for this study comprises of 665 primary school teachers in the 45 public primary schools in Awka South LGEA. The sample for this study comprised of 150 teachers, using the simple random sampling techniques. The researcher developed a 23-item structured questionnaire titled "Teachers Perception of Storytelling Strategy for Improving Reading Comprehension Questionnaire" (TPSSIRCQ). Reliability test was conducted using Cronbach Alpha to ascertain the internal consistency and a reliability index of 0.93, 0.76 and 0.82 were obtained for the three clusters. A four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4,3,2, and 1 were used to answer the research questions. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions. Mean response of 2.50 and above were regarded as agree while the mean response of below 2.50 were regarded as disagree. Findings from the study revealed that boosting listening among others are the benefits of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. The findings of this study also revealed that pupils may not find storytelling engaging especially if they are not interested in the story and inadequate resources among others are the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. Finally, findings from the study revealed that using prior knowledge and identifying the main ideas among others are the storytelling strategies are used by teachers for improving primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. It was recommended among others that teachers should attend trainings and workshops to learn different method of teaching.

Keywords: Primary education, storytelling, academic achievement, Reading Comprehension, English studies

Introduction

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Primary education is a component of the basic education. It is the first six years of basic education in Nigeria and targeted at children from 5 to 11 years. This level of education stands as a foundation upon which the rest of the education system is built upon. It is therefore, the key to the success or failure of the whole system of education. Primary education is designed to prepare the child for other higher levels of education. In many countries, primary education is compulsory for all children. In Nigeria, primary education is free, reducing the financial burden on parents and ensuring that every child has access to basic education, regardless of their background.

Primary education prepares children for secondary education, which is the next stage of formal education. The National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN 2013), describes primary education as education given in an institution for children aged normally 6 to 11+. In this study, primary education is education given to children in an organized institution from 5 years plus. Primary education focuses on developing basic literacy and numeracy skills, which are essential for future academic success. Primary education also places a strong emphasis on developing social and emotional skills, such as teamwork, communication and problem-solving.

Primary education is designed to prepare the child for other higher levels of education. The general objectives of primary education according to the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013) includes; The inculcation of permanent literacy and numeracy, and the ability to communicate effectively; The laying of a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking; Citizenship education as a basis for scientific effective participation in and contribution to the life of the society; Character and moral training and the development of sound attitudes; Developing in the child the ability to adapt to his changing environment; Giving the child opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable him to function effectively in the society within the limits of his capacity; and Providing basic tools for further educational advancement, including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality.

To achieve the above laudable objectives, according to the National Policy on Education, the primary school curriculum shall include: Languages such as Language of the

environment, English and French; Mathematics; Science; Physical and Health Education; Religious Knowledge; Agriculture/Home Economics; Social Studies and Citizenship Education; and Cultural and Creative Arts (Drawing, Handicraft, Music and Cultural Activities). As stated in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), the primary education shall be tuition free, universal and compulsory. Teaching shall be by practical, exploratory and experimental methods. In addition, the medium of instruction shall be language of the environment for the first three years. During this period, English shall be taught as a subject.

A closer look at the first general objective will show that the document recognizes the need to lay solid foundation for the child to be able to communicate effectively. This aligns with the last objective which is aimed to prepare the child for further advancement. Thus, teaching reading comprehension in English Studies is one measure to develop the communication capacity of the primary school child. To achieve this, the primary school children are engaged in literacy activities.

Reading is the backbone of education and as such, an activity that requires focus, interest, motivation and continuous effort. Reading is an active receptive skill that comprises the interaction between the reader and the text to be read where comprehension and analyses of information presented in the text are required (Okonkwo and Danner cited in Abubakar and Abdullahi, 2022). It is a complex activity that involves sight, intelligence, knowledge of the writer's language and knowledge of the word. For beginners, reading is the ability to recognize that printed symbols represent speech and to respond to the sounds and meanings of words. Reading goes with comprehension; and reading without comprehension means no reading at all.

Reading comprehension means the ability to read, process, and understand the meaning of a text, message or any written or printed material or document. According to Rutzler (2020), reading comprehension is the ability to read, understand, process and recall what was just read. Reading comprehension requires the construction of a coherent mental representation of the information in a text (Butterfuss, Kim and Kendeou, 2020). Teaching reading comprehension to primary school pupils requires a multifaceted approach that considers their developmental

stage, interests, and learning styles. Effective programmes for teaching reading comprehension strategies most often involve direct and explicit reading strategy instruction and incorporate techniques of metacognitive modelling, collaborative use of the strategy in action, guided practice, and independent use of the strategy so learners can reach their fullest potential (Duke and Pearson, cited in Jakobson, Soodla and Aro 2022). Teachers teach pupils how to use these strategies effectively through modeling and guided practice. Teachers also use graphic organizers like story maps, Venn diagrams, and concept webs to visually represent the structure of texts and help pupils organize their thoughts (Archer and Hughes, cited in Bogaerds-Hazenberg, Evers-Vermeul, and van den Bergs, 2021). Graphic organizers provide a visual framework for understanding the text. Teachers also encourage active reading by teaching pupils to visualize, make predictions, and monitor their comprehension while reading (Keene and Zimmermann, 2017). By doing this, teachers provide opportunities for pupils to engage in discussions and peer interactions to deepen their understanding of the text.

In spite of these available strategies employed by teachers to improve pupils' reading comprehension, it has been observed that reading comprehension remains one area in English studies primary school pupils experience difficulty. In Anambra state, Nigeria, pupils who struggle with reading can be found in primary schools (Anidi, Obidike and Anyachebelu (2023). According to the Anidi, Obidike and Anyachebelu, this has become worrisome that parents often employ the services of home tutors to basically review what has been taught in school: perhaps the child might assimilate reading skills on a second teaching attempts. It therefore, requires conscious efforts to effectively teach reading comprehension. The chalk and talk method of teaching which has been the conventional way of teaching may not suffice for the effective teaching of reading comprehension. There is need for a teaching strategy to be used. Teaching strategy can be seen as a plan method, or series of activities designed to achieve a particular goal. Teaching strategy employed by teachers in the classrooms play an important role in learners' achievement in a subject. Teachers' choice of strategy can make or mar the intended learning outcome. One strategy that could be tried and which is not strange or difficult to utilize is storytelling.

The storytelling strategy involves using narrative elements to enhance reading comprehension and engage pupils in meaningful discussions about texts. Storytelling as a strategy involves teachers or pupils orally recounting stories, anecdotes, or narratives related to the content being studied (Archer and Hughes, cited in Bogaerds-Hazenberg, Evers-Vermeul, and van den Bergs, 2021). Storytelling refers to a method that conveys or shares a narrative or sequence of events through words, images, or other forms of communication. In this study, storytelling is seen as the interactive art of using words and actions to reveal the imagines of a story while encouraging the listener's imagination. It can be used across various subjects, including language arts, social studies, and science, to make abstract concepts more concrete and memorable for pupils. Through storytelling, teachers can bring characters, events, and themes to life, stimulating pupils' imagination and fostering emotional connections with the material. Storytelling can therefore be use to teach at the primary school level. It is usually provided through the presentation of characters, settings, conflicts, and resolutions within a structured narrative framework while utilizing various elements such as plot, dialogue, description, and imagery to engage the audience and convey a message or meaning (Khamsuk and Whanchit, 2021). Storytelling is an effective teaching strategy for children to enhance their reading abilities and engagement with the material (Fitri and Ginting, 2021). Additionally, listening to stories during learning promotes creativity, empathy, self-confidence, and overall cognitive and emotional growth (Hammond, 2015; Sitaresmi and Ginting, 2022). Additionally, storytelling encourages pupils to make connections between the text and their own lives, promoting deeper understanding and critical thinking. Based on this, the researchers want to find out if storytelling strategy can help pupils in achieving the reading comprehension which maybe could lead to academic achievement in reading comprehension.

Achievement can be seen as what one gains at the end of a programme. Achievement denotes the amount of learning that has occurred relative to stated objectives in the cognitive domain. Academic achievement indicates the set of learned knowledge, the degree of growth of capacities, and skills in the academic setting (Jeynes cited in Al-Abyadh and Abdel Azeem (2022). In the context of this study, academic achievement is viewed as the extent to which

pupils are able to acquire the reading comprehension skills relative to stated objectives. In Anambra State, primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension has not been encouraging. This may be as a result of the challenges teachers' face in teaching reading comprehension to pupils in primary school. Some of the challenges includes: limited teacher training, lack of engaging materials, time constraints among others. Breneman (2018) state that teachers may lack training in storytelling techniques and effective reading comprehension strategies. Harris (2015) is of the view that using diverse, culturally relevant stories can help the pupils to be engaged in reading comprehension. The researchers therefore, wants to find out teachers' perception of story-telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South Local Government Education Authority (LGEA).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Reading comprehension is the heart of academic activities. The foundation for reading comprehension is laid at the primary school level to enable pupils achieve well not only in reading comprehension component of the English studies, but in other subjects of study where they must read, comprehend and answer the questions posed to them.

Unfortunately, it has been observed that many pupils find reading comprehension difficult. Even at primary five, pupils still struggle to read and comprehend texts within their comprehension level. This situation is likely to affect their overall achievement in school. Although teachers make effort in this direction, it appears that the strategies employed by teachers have not yielded the expected results in achievement and retention of learning as reflected in pupils' scores and performances in reading comprehension tasks. This study therefore, seeks to determine teachers' perception of story-telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA.

Purpose of the Study

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The main purpose of the study was to determine teachers' perception of story-telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA. Specifically, the study intends to determine;

1. Benefits of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA.
2. Challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA.
3. Possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What are the benefits of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?
2. What are the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?
3. What are the possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?

Methods

This study was carried out to determine teachers' perception of story-telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies Awka South LGEA. Three research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population for this study comprises of 665 primary school teachers in the 45 public primary schools in Awka South LGEA. The sample for this study comprised of 150 teachers, using the simple random sampling technique. The researcher

developed a 23-item structured questionnaire titled “Teachers Perception of Storytelling Strategy for Improving Reading Comprehension Questionnaire” (TPSSIRCQ). The instrument was face validated by three experts, two in the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation unit of the Department of Educational Foundations all from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Reliability test was conducted using Cronbach Alpha to ascertain the internal consistency and a reliability index of 0.93, 0.76 and 0.82 were obtained for the three clusters. A four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4,3,2, and 1 were used to answer the research questions. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions. Mean response of 2.50 and above were regarded as agree while the mean response of below 2.50 were regarded as disagree.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the benefits of using story telling strategy for improving pupils’ academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?

Table 1: Mean scores of respondents on the benefits of using story telling strategy for improving pupils’ academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA

S/N	Benefits of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils’ reading comprehension	X	SD	Decision
1.	Boosts listening and comprehension skills of pupils	3.91	0.96	Agree
2.	Storytelling helps develop a child’s imagination	3.57	0.68	Agree
3.	It improves pupils’ ability to communicate	3.96	0.70	Agree
4.	Storytelling expands children’s vocabulary	3.52	0.60	Agree
5.	Storytelling boosts children’s memory	3.38	0.83	Agree
6.	It helps pupils to become active listeners	3.53	0.64	Agree
7.	Storytelling helps children to learn fast	3.55	0.71	Agree
8.	Storytelling introduces children to the world beyond their environment	3.36	0.77	Agree
9.	It helps children develop a sense of empathy	3.16	0.90	Agree
10.	It fosters critical thinking	3.26	0.89	Agree
11.	Storytelling during learning promotes creativity	3.38	0.73	Agree
Grand Mean		3.50	0.76	Agree

Result in Table 1 shows that the items listed on the benefits of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA were agreed by respondents with mean ratings ranging from 3.16 to 3.96. The cluster mean score of 3.50 means that respondents agreed to all items so listed. The standard deviations for all the items are within 0.64 to 0.96. This shows that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Research Question 2: What are the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?

Table 2: Mean scores of respondents on the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA

S/N	Challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils in reading comprehension	X	SD	Decision
12	Pupils may not find storytelling engaging especially if they are not interested in the story	3.78	0.44	Agree
13.	Pupils with short attention spans may struggle to focus on longer stories	3.14	0.91	Agrees
13	Using storytelling strategies takes too much time away from other reading instruction	3.90	0.35	Agree
14	Managing a large class while using storytelling as a teaching tool can be challenging	3.97	0.53	Agree
15	Inadequate teachers training on how to make use of storytelling strategy	3.74	0.69	Agree
16	Inadequate resources	2.96	0.29	Agree
Grand Mean		3.58	0.53	Agree

Result in Table 2 shows that the six items listed on challenges of using story telling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA were agreed by respondents with mean ratings ranging from 2.96 to 3.97. The grand mean of 3.58 means that respondents agreed to the items so listed as the challenges of using storytelling strategies. The standard deviations for all the items are within 0.29 to 0.91. this shows that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Research Questions 3: What are the possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils’ academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA?

Table 3: Mean scores of respondents on the possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils’ academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA.

S/N	Possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils’ reading comprehension	X	SD	Decision
17.	Involving pupils in story selection	3.13	0.88	Agree
18.	Using shorter stories or breaking them into smaller chunks	3.38	0.73	Agree
19.	Adapting stories to suit pupils’ reading levels	3.54	0.57	Agree
20.	Encouraging pupils to share their own stories	3.55	0.71	Agree
21.	Monitor pupil participation and engagement	3.36	0.77	Agree
22.	Providing background information	2.50	0.68	Agree
23.	Providing professional development opportunities for teachers	3.65	0.57	Agree
Grand Mean		3.30	0.70	Agree

Results in Table 3 shows the Possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils’ reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA. The respondents agreed to all the items so listed as the possible solutions to the challenges of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils’ reading comprehension. This result also shows the grand mean of 3.30 which shows that the respondents agreed to the items so listed. The standard deviations for all the items are within 0.57 to 0.88, this shows that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that boosting listening and comprehension skills of pupils, storytelling helps develop a child’s imagination, improving pupils’ ability to communicate and storytelling expands children’s vocabulary among others are the benefits of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils’ academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA. These findings are in line with that of Hammond, (2015); Sitaresmi and Ginting, (2022) who posits that listening to stories during learning promotes creativity, empathy, self-confidence, and overall cognitive

and emotional growth. Storytelling is a natural way for the teacher to build engagement, reinforce comprehension strategies to pupils who have not yet mastered decoding, and explore cultures from around the world. With the benefits of these storytelling, it is therefore necessary that teachers make use of the storytelling strategy to help in improving primary school pupils reading comprehension.

The findings of this study also revealed that storytelling may not engage pupils with different learning styles and ensuring that stories align with specific learning objectives and outcomes can be challenging among others are the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA. These findings are in consonance with that of Breneman (2018), who posits that teachers may lack training in storytelling techniques and effective reading comprehension strategies. Findings are also in agreement with that of Gambrell (2015), who posits that sustaining pupil's engagement and motivation throughout the storytelling process can be challenging. Despite these challenges, storytelling remains a powerful tool for engaging pupils and enhancing the academic achievement.

Finally, findings from the study revealed that Involving pupils in story selection using shorter stories or breaking them into smaller chunks and adapting stories to suit pupils' reading levels among others are the possible solutions to the challenges of using story telling strategy for improving primary school pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in English studies in Awka South LGEA. These findings are in line with that of Madondo and Dampier (2021) who posits that as learners engaged in different storytelling activities, they recycled words, phrases and utterances acquired from the educators and/or peers. Also, Breneman (2018) posits that providing workshops and training for teachers on storytelling techniques will help to curb the challenge of using storytelling strategy in teaching reading comprehension. Findings of the study also are in agreement with that of Harris (2015) who posits that using diverse, culturally relevant stories can help the pupils to be engaged in reading comprehension.

Conclusion

This study is on the teachers' perception of storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Teachers agreed to the benefits of using storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. Teacher agreed to the items listed as the challenges of storytelling strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. Also, teachers agreed to some of the items listed as the strategy for improving pupils' academic achievement in reading comprehension. Storytelling has been found to be a promising instructional strategy as well as a growing study domain in education. Story telling has also being useful to pupils.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Teachers should make use of storytelling strategy to teach pupils in school as it is a very effective strategy for teaching reading comprehension.
2. State government should help in providing resource materials use in teaching reading comprehension to pupils through storytelling.
3. State government should organize, seminars, workshops and conferences for teachers on how to make use of the storytelling strategy and other innovative strategies in teaching reading comprehension in school.

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